

Molecular States of Some N-Monoalkyl and N, N'-Dialkyl-Substituted Aliphatic Amides in Solvents of Different Polarity and Hydrogen Bonding*

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Molecular states of some hydrogen-bonded N-monoalkyl and non-hydrogen-bonded, N,N'-dialkyl substituted aliphatic amides, have been studied in benzene, nitrobenzene and water from the cryscopic measurements. The results indicate that the molecular self-association of the polar hydrogen-bonded solutes occurs both in the non-polar (benzene) as well as in the polar and non-hydrogen bonded (nitrobenzene) solvents. Polar non-hydrogen-bonded solutes, (N,N'-dialkyl substituted amides), do not undergo self-association in any one of these solvents. No appreciable association of the polar hydrogen-bonded or of the polar non-hydrogen-bonded solutes, appears to occur in the hydrogen-bonded solvents like water.

Association of N-monoalkyl substituted aliphatic amides in non-polar solvents like benzene, carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexane etc., has been studied spectroscopically by a number of workers¹⁻⁴. Some non-spectroscopic techniques have also been employed to investigate the molecular states of the amides and the substituted amides in non-polar solvents⁵⁻⁷. However, a comparative study of the molecular states of these compounds in non-polar and polar (with and without hydrogen bonding) solvents, does not appear to have been undertaken. Such a study should yield valuable information about the nature of molecular interactions in presence of different molecular environments. This situation prompted an investigation of the molecular states of the N-mono and N,N'-dialkyl substituted aliphatic amides, e.g., N-methylformamide (NMF), N-methylacetamide, (NMA), N-methylpropionamide (NMP), N-ethylformamide (NEF), N-butylacetamide (NBA) and N,N'-dimethylformamide (DMF), in benzene (non-polar and non-hydrogen-bonded), nitrobenzene (polar and non-hydrogen bonded) and water (polar and hydrogen-bonded), by determining the apparent molecular weights of these solutes from the measurement of the depression in the freezing point of the solvent concerned.

* This work, in part, has been supported by the CSIR, India and the Society of the Sigma Xi of USA.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Purification of materials :

(i) Benzene (B.D.H.) was purified by shaking the sample with about 10% of its volume of H_2SO_4 (A.R., Conc.). The process was repeated several times. The final product was washed with distilled water and dried over quicklime for twenty-four hours and then distilled. The final purification was done by fractional crystallisation. The m.p. of the purified sample was 5.50° (literature value : 5.53°)⁸.

(ii) Nitrobenzene (B.D.H.) was distilled, using an air condenser, and the distillate was left over freshly ignited quicklime overnight and then again distilled. Finally, it was purified by fractional crystallisation. The m.p. of the product was 5.65° (given : 5.68°)⁸.

(iii) The amides, used in the present investigation, were purified in the usual manner, as described elsewhere⁹. Samples having conductance 10^{-6} mho or less, in every case, were used. After purification they were stored in dark-coloured bottles and kept in a dry box to reduce moisture and light effects to a minimum. The samples were usually used on the next day after distillation.

Depressions in the freezing points were measured in the usual manner, using a Beckmann thermometer. The freezing point depressions, thus obtained (usually mean of three consecutive readings or more), were used to calculate the apparent molecular weights. Concentrations usually varied from 0.05 to 0.5 molal.

FIG. 1 SOLVENT - BENZENE

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to economise space, the results have been summarised in Figs. 1-3, in which the association factor ' f ' *i.e.*, the ratio of the apparent molecular weight, M , to the formula molecular weight, M_0 has been plotted against concentration in different cases.

The results have been discussed solvent-wise for the sake of convenience.

(a) *Benzene*

It appears from Fig. 1 that for the N-monoalkyl substituted amides, the apparent molecular weight, M , is higher than the corresponding formula molecular weight, M_0 , in every case and the higher the concentration, the larger the values of M . This indicates that these amides are highly associated in benzene. On the other hand, a N,N'-dialkyl substituted amide, like DMF, shows a quite different behaviour; the ratio M/M_0 remains very close to unity at all the concentrations studied here. In other words, DMF remains almost un-associated in this solvent. It is well-known that DMF is almost unassociated even in the pure liquid state. This difference in the behaviours of the mono- and dialkyl substituted amides shows that the hydrogen-bonded inter-molecular association is favoured in the presence of the surrounding nonpolar molecules. If the hydrogen bonding is absent, in the pure solute, as in DMF, no self-association occurs in presence of the non-polar molecules.

(b) *Nitrobenzene*

Fig. 2 clearly shows that the apparent molecular weight M of NMF, NMA, NMP, NEF, NBA, is higher than the corresponding formula molecular weight M_0 ; also M increases with the increase in concentration in every case although the increase is not so rapid as in benzene solutions. It seems that some dipolar interaction between the solvent (dipole

Fig. 2 SOLVENT: NITROBENZENE.

moment $\mu = 4.27D$) and the solute molecules, counteracts the tendency of self-association of the solute through hydrogen bonding and so, the value of M/M_0 in nitrobenzene does not rise as rapidly as in benzene. Again the absence of hydrogen bonding in the pure solute (DMF), does not favour association of DMF in this solvent.

FIG. 3. SOLVENT: WATER

(c) Water

It may be noted with interest that the M of the N-monoalkyl-substituted amides, in water, is almost the same as the corresponding M_0 , within the concentration range studied here. This is in sharp contrast to the results in benzene and in nitrobenzene. However, DMF is unassociated even in water as in the other two solvents. The normal molecular weights of the N-monoalkyl substituted amides in water are, apparently, due to a strong N—H...O bonding interaction between the amide and water molecules, leading to the disruption of the weaker hydrogen-bonded association of the compounds in the pure state *i.e.*, the solute-solvent hydrogen bonding disturbs the intermolecular association of the amide molecules themselves and leads to the water-N-monoalkyl-substituted amide association and formation of amide monomers.

The deviation from the ideal behaviour can be examined in a more impressive manner from the point of activity of the solute. The activity coefficient, γ , of the solute is related to the freezing point depression, ΔT_f , by the expression,

$$\ln \gamma = (\phi_m - 1) + \int_0^m \frac{\phi_m - 1}{m} dm \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$\phi_m = \frac{\Delta T_f}{K_f \cdot m \cdot \nu} \quad \dots (2)$$

The terms used have their usual significance. The integral in (1) can be evaluated graphically and thus γ can be calculated. The values of γ , thus obtained, at two concentrations (the maximum and minimum studied here) for the NMF-solvent and DMF-solvent systems, are given in Table I. The results for other N-monoalkyl substituted amides are similar to those for NMF and hence have been omitted to economise space.

TABLE I

System	Conc. (m)	γ	System	Conc. (m)	γ
NMF/C ₆ H ₆	0.095	0.646	NMF/water	0.197	0.996
	0.427	0.244		0.558	0.958
DMF/C ₆ H ₆	0.150	0.993	DMF/water	0.135	0.974
	0.480	0.854		0.546	0.801
NMF/C ₆ H ₅ NO ₂	0.093	0.722	DMF/C ₆ H ₅ NO ₂	0.125	0.981
	0.531	0.364		0.546	0.800

It may be noted from Table I that γ decreases very rapidly with the increase in concentration in the case of N-monoalkyl-substituted amides in the non-polar solvents but remains almost stationary in the hydrogen-bonded solvents in which the deviation from the ideal behaviour appears to be rather small. However, γ of a dialkyl-substituted amide, like DMF, decreases only slightly with the increase in concentration, both in the hydrogen-bonded and non-hydrogen bonded solvents, perhaps, due to weak dipolar interactions.

Although the results obtained here have been satisfactorily explained from the concepts of hydrogen bonding and activity coefficient, it would be interesting to inquire whether the internal pressures of the two components of the systems can throw some light on the problem. It is well-known that an appreciable difference in the internal pressures of the two components of a molecular solution should cause large deviations from the ideal behaviour. In view of the highly polar nature of the solutes, examined here, and the possibility of hydrogen bond formation in some of them, the distribution of molecules in these liquid solutes will not be completely random. In such a case, the internal pressure, $(\partial E/\partial V)_T$, can not be taken to be even approximately equal to $\Delta E/V$. Hence the estimation of the internal pressures of such liquids can not be made¹⁰. However, from the data on internal pressures, already reported¹¹ for acetamide and some other hydrogen-bonded liquids, it can be safely concluded that the internal pressures of the N-monoalkyl substituted aliphatic amides must be considerably larger than either of pure benzene or of nitrobenzene. The data, given in Table II, have been reproduced here from Mortimer's paper¹¹ and makes the point quite clear.

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11. F. S. Mortimer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 633.

TABLE II

Compound	Internal pressure relative to naphthalene
C_6H_6	0.94
C_6H_5Cl	0.98 (it is reasonable to assume that the internal pressure of nitrobenzene will be of this order)
Water	4.6
Acetamide	3.8
Methyl alcohol	3.35
Ethyl alcohol	2.9

The large difference in the internal pressures of the hydrogen-bonded and non-hydrogen-bonded compounds is quite obvious from Table II. This difference would give rise to a tendency of self-isolation for each of the two molecular species present in solution and, if the hydrogen-bond formation is possible in one of the species (as in the N-monoalkyl substituted amides), molecular association of such a compound would occur, leading to negative deviation from the ideal behaviour. If the hydrogen bond formation and self-association are not possible, separation of the two components is likely to occur.

We thus see that the study of the activity coefficients and the internal pressures support the conclusions arrived at from a study of the apparent molecular weights. It must be emphasised that the major factor governing the deviation from the ideal behaviour, on the molecular level, appears to be the possibility of the hydrogen bond formation in some and its impossibility in other substances.

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Received August 12, 1968
Revised MSS received November 4, 1969.